

Towards fully autonomous ship hull inspection for security relevant attached objects using AUVs equipped with imaging sensors

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Abstract— This publication presents an approach to autonomous ship hull inspection using autonomous underwater vehicles (AUVs) for the detection and identification of safety-critical foreign objects in support of innovative maritime security technologies. The proposed contribution addresses a field of growing relevance for the safety and protection of maritime infrastructure and operations. The approach is based on a novel navigation framework that enables adaptive, structure-relative maneuvering along submerged surfaces using a proprietary relative object navigation method. Experimental results from real-world deployments are presented to assess system performance under operational conditions.

The results demonstrate the feasibility of the approach for practical maritime applications. Current limitations are analyzed, and directions for system optimization as well as future work are outlined.

I. INTRODUCTION

In the context of the increasingly tense geopolitical security environment, the protection of maritime shipping is gaining growing importance. In addition to threat scenarios involving the damage or destruction of seagoing vessels through explosive devices attached to ship hulls, maritime smuggling using containers placed at various locations on the hull is also on the rise. These scenarios require the most comprehensive possible inspection of ship hulls for suspicious security-relevant objects to support hazard prevention and crime control.

So far, ship hull inspections have predominantly been carried out by divers or remotely operated vehicles (ROVs). When underwater visibility conditions are favorable, visual documentation of the hull and any detected findings are possible. In situations of limited visibility, however, divers must rely on tactile search methods to identify potential foreign objects. Even under good visibility conditions, these conventional inspection procedures are highly time-consuming and often fail to achieve complete coverage of the hull surface. In regions with persistently poor visibility, such as many ports in Northern Europe, their effectiveness is therefore severely limited.

Due to their considerable time requirements, the inspection methods described above are typically limited to random checks of arriving vessels, resulting in a level of scrutiny that is not commensurate with the significance of the underlying risk. To significantly increase inspection density and thereby improve threat mitigation, the use of autonomous inspection methods based on AUVs is a promising approach. These systems can rapidly and efficiently inspect ship hulls,

for example while anchorage before port entry, and detect and even classify relevant objects.

Subdron intends to deploy autonomous underwater vehicles to enhance the efficiency and accuracy of underwater inspections for port and ship safety applications. This publication presents the technical implementation, discusses the specific challenges encountered, and reports the results obtained from the authors' practical tests. In addition, the findings are analyzed in detail, and the next steps toward the development of a fully autonomous ship hull inspection system are outlined.

II. METHODS

For autonomous ship hull inspection, Subdron employs the Sparus II AUV platform provided by Iqua Robotics [1]. Autonomous navigation along the hull is achieved using a proprietary Relative Object Navigation (RON) system, which is currently under patent application [2].

RON combines dedicated hardware and software that enable an underwater vehicle to navigate in close proximity to a structure while acquiring high-resolution data. The approach decouples the sensors used for environmental perception and navigation from the sensors used for target scanning. This separation is advantageous because the navigation sensors can operate at longer range and lower resolution than the scanning sensors, allowing the vehicle to remain localized even when the scanning sensors are unable to acquire valid measurement data.

The system employs two compact imaging sonars (Impact Subsea ISS360 [3]) that continuously survey the environment over 360 degrees as the vehicle moves. The resulting sonar data are processed by a sequence of algorithms that filter, cluster, and classify geometric primitives, such as planes, curves, and isolated points, and fit them to predefined structural categories (e.g. vessels, port walls, the seafloor, or pillars). Once the target structure has been identified, the system generates a trajectory and guides the vehicle along it while maintaining the optimal standoff distance and sensor orientation to ensure continuous acquisition of high-resolution data and complete structural coverage.

In addition, the RON system is sensor-flexible. It requires as input the optimal target distance, the field of view of the scanning sensors, and, if necessary, the desired data overlap. On this basis, RON computes the inspection trajectory and adapts vehicle navigation in real time to support data quality and coverage consistency.

For the application defined in this paper, the vehicle's integrated sensor payload for object and structural inspection comprises optical camera systems from DeepWater Exploration [4], including illumination units, as well as a high-resolution acoustic multibeam echosounder (MBES) from Imagenex [5]. Depending on the underwater visibility conditions, subdron applies two different inspection strategies for ship hulls and port infrastructure.

In environments with sufficient visibility, such as Mediterranean ports or anchorage areas, high-resolution optical cameras are used in combination with the acoustic sonar system to acquire inspection data. Both data streams can be recorded simultaneously and subsequently overlaid to achieve the highest possible measurement accuracy. In underwater environments with visibility below approximately one meter, the acoustic MBES alone provides sufficient data for inspection purposes.

By combining the acquired sensor data with the vehicle's precise position information at the time of measurement, photomosaics and 3D point cloud representations of the ship hull can be generated. Figure 1 shows the AUV equipped with the optical and acoustic sensor payload for the inspection of ship hulls and port infrastructure. The front section of the AUV carries the camera system with integrated light source, indicated by the two round elements, as well as the MBES sensor, shown as the rectangular unit. Depending on the application, additional cameras and lights can be mounted on the upper part of the AUV's front section to capture imagery during navigation beneath the ship hull.

Figure 1. AUV with optical and acoustic sensor payload for inspection of ship hulls and port infrastructure.

Potentially suspicious objects on the hull can be extracted from the photomosaic and point-cloud data and examined in greater detail if required. In addition, anomaly detection can be automated using machine learning methods, thereby further increasing the efficiency of the inspection workflow. The location and dimensions of such objects can be estimated with high accuracy, enabling divers to retrieve or inspect them more easily in a subsequent step.

III. FIELD MEASUREMENTS

To evaluate the inspection technology under real-world conditions, measurements were conducted on the research vessel *Elisabeth Mann Borgese* [6], operated by the Leibniz Institute for Baltic Research Warnemünde (IOW), in the port

of Rostock. Figure 2 shows the vessel in port. The ship has a length of 56.5 m and a draft of 3.65 m.

Figure 2. IOW ship *Elisabeth Mann Borgese* in port of Rostock.

The measurements were performed using the AUV connected via cable to a floating buoy equipped with a Wi-Fi antenna. This configuration enables the recorded navigation parameters and measurement data to be viewed and preliminarily analyzed during the dive. Figure 3 shows the AUV together with the Wi-Fi buoy for live data monitoring.

Figure 3. AUV with towed Wi-Fi buoy and cable connection for live data view.

To assess the system's imaging capabilities, two objects were attached to the ship's hull to represent examples of suspicious objects, such as smuggling containers or explosive charges. Figure 4 shows the first object: a 60 cm long plastic tube with a diameter of 10 cm, filled with stones and sealed watertight. Figure 5 shows the second object: a watertight plastic canister filled with sand, measuring $20 \times 30 \times 10$ cm. Both objects were suspended in front of the ship's side at a distance of approximately 3 m from each other using ropes attached to the railing. The objects were positioned approximately 1 m below the water surface.

Figure 4. Object 1: plastic tube; dimensions: 60 cm length, 10 cm diameter; filled with stones and water sealed

Figure 5. Object 2: plastic canister; dimensions: 20 x 30 x 10 cm; filled with sand and water sealed.

The AUV autonomously executed several trajectories along the ship's side using RON at a distance of approximately 1.5 m from the hull at varying depths up to 2.5 m. During the measurement, the ship's water outlet was operational, which was also detectable in the recorded measurement data. Figure 6 shows the measurement setup with the autonomously navigating AUV (1), the active water outlet (2), and the measurement object (3) suspended by ropes.

Figure 6. Inspection of ship hull.
 (1) Diving AUV moving along ship hull.
 (2) Active water outlet of the ship.
 (3) Object hung from the ship wall.

Due to poor underwater visibility, no usable optical image data could be recorded during the measurements. Also, no measurements were performed beneath the hull due to insufficient under-keel clearance.

IV. RESULTS

The processed and reconstructed measurement data is presented in the following figures. The results of the acoustic measurements are displayed as a point cloud representation. The image shows the ship's hull with an interrupted bilge keel. The measurement objects were already detectable in the raw live data transmitted during the mission and are marked in red in the subsequent images for clarity. In this case, the detection of the measurement objects was performed manually; however, automation of this process is planned for future work.

Figure 7. Point cloud representation of the inspected ship side.

Figure 8. Point cloud representation detail.
 (1) Object 1.
 (2) Object 2.
 (3) Air bubbles from active water outlet.

The recorded and processed measurement data can be spatially quantified using data visualization software (here: NaviModel from EIVA [7]). The identified measurement

objects exhibited dimensions that closely matched their actual size (Figures 9 and 10). Due to the movement of the test objects during the inspection, object 1 (the tube) appears vertically elongated.

Figure 9. Detail view of object 1 with scale.

Figure 10. Detailed view of object 2 with scale.

Under adequate underwater visibility conditions, optical image data can be recorded simultaneously with the acoustic measurements and subsequently assembled into photomosaics. Figure 11 shows such a photomosaic of a ship's side. To improve object detection on the ship's hull, both imaging modalities can be superimposed and analyzed jointly.

Figure 11. Photomosaic from ship hull.

V. DISCUSSION & FUTURE WORK

The measurements conducted under real-world conditions demonstrate the technology's suitability for detecting foreign objects on ship hulls within relevant size ranges. In poor visibility conditions, suspicious objects can be identified in the acoustic measurement data, whereas in good visibility conditions, optical image data can additionally be employed to improve object detection.

However, a key limitation of the current technology is the exclusion of complex ship hull areas like rudder and propeller regions. Due to the maneuverability characteristics of the Sparus AUV, these regions of the underwater hull are generally difficult to inspect, as collisions cannot be ruled out and not all areas can be adequately mapped. To fully inspect all areas of the ship's hull, the use of AUVs with adapted maneuverability is advisable.

To address this limitation, comprehensive inspection concepts should consider the coordinated use of heterogeneous AUV platforms. A torpedo-shaped vehicle is well suited for efficient coverage of large, planar hull sections, while a hovering-type AUV can provide safe and precise inspection of confined or complex geometries such as rudders, propellers, and irregular structures. In addition, the hovering platform can support targeted re-inspection and high-resolution characterization of candidate anomalies identified during the initial survey.

Building on this, a collaborative multi-vehicle inspection framework combined with automated anomaly detection has the potential to enable fully autonomous, end-to-end ship hull inspection for foreign object detection. Future work will therefore focus on (i) integrating a hovering AUV into the existing system architecture, including mission planning and inter-vehicle coordination, and (ii) advancing (automated) anomaly detection methods by incorporating and fusing acoustic data with optical image data to improve robustness under varying environmental conditions.

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